

Research article

‘Pig’ in Bantu

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Abstract: This brief report provides an overview of geographic distribution of words denoting ‘pig’ in Bantu languages. While reflexes of the Proto-Bantu reconstructed form **-gòdòbè* are widely spread in Eastern Bantu zones, forms traced back to the (shortened) PB form **-gòdó* are dominantly distributed in Western Bantu zones. This article also provides information on several forms that are only locally observed especially in North Eastern languages.

Keywords: ‘pig’, geographical distribution, Bantu languages, Proto-Bantu, Niger-Congo

1. Introduction

The present paper aims to present a brief overview of geographical distribution of words denoting ‘pig’ in present Bantu languages. The data are mostly based on the two online lexical databases, namely the ‘Bantu Lexical Reconstructions 3’ (Bastin *et al.* 2002) and the ‘Tanzanian Language survey’, which is a digital compilation of vocabulary lists of Eastern Bantu languages originally collected by Derek Nurse and Gérard Philippson in the early 70’s (Nurse and Philippson 1975).

2. General distribution of the reconstructed forms

In the list of Proto-Bantu lexicon by Meeussen (1969), a lexical form for ‘pig’ is reconstructed as **-gòdòbè* [BLR-MAIN-1494] (as registered in Bastin *et al.* (2002)), which has two shortened variants with a slight difference of vowel height, namely **-gòdó* [BLR-MAIN-1493] and **-gùdú* [BLR-MAIN-1536].

As a general distributional tendency, these two types show the ‘East vs. West’ distribution pattern. The longer form **-gòdòbè* and its descendant forms are widely spread in the Eastern Bantu area including zones D, E, F, G, J, L, M, N, P, R, and S (for the Bantu zones, see Guthrie 1967–71; Maho 2009; Hammarström 2019), e.g., in Holoholo [D28b] *ηoloβε*, Bungu [JD53] *inguluwe*, Embu [E52] *ngorwe*, Bende [F12] *ngulubhe*, Luguru [G35] *nguluwe*, Luba [L31a] *ηulube*, Ila [M63] *tfulube*, Ngindo [P14] *ligolobe*, Ngandjera [R24] *siηguruβε*, Sethoto [S33] *k’olobe*.

On the other hand, the shortened forms are exclusively distributed in the Western zones including zones A, B, C, H, K, L, and R, e.g., in Bulu-Bene [A74] *ηgoe*, Nzadi [B865] *ηgùl*, Lingala [C30B] *ngùlu*, Congo-Yoombi [H16c] *yingulu*, Luwena-Lubale [K14] *ηgulu*, Pende [L11] *ηgulu*, Khumbi [R14] *ocingulu*.

This ‘East vs. West’ distribution is quite suggestive about the process of historical development considering the distribution pattern attested e.g., in the case of ‘chicken’ (Shinagawa and Komori 2022b), which is divided into ‘North-West vs. the rest’, as it may suggest these patterns reflect different stages in the process of ‘Bantu expansion’ (for a current discussion of the migration route, see de Filippo *et al.* 2012, Grollemund *et al.* 2015, among others).

3. Local variation

A closer look at the Eastern belt reveals more variation. For example, a number of forms descended from **-gòdòbè* take another shortened form that drops the syllable in the middle. The forms, which we tentatively label as *<gubi>*, are rather limitedly distributed in zones E, G, and P such as in Kilimanjaro Bantu (Chaga) languages [E60] *nguwe*, in Hehe [G62] *ingubi*, and in Matumbi [P13] *ngobe*.

There are also many different forms which are only shared in a very closely related group of languages, which might be seen as a local lexical innovation. An interesting distribution is observed around the Lake Victoria, where there are at least three clusters of languages that share a common form denoting ‘pig’. In the northern area, *<mbizi>* and its related forms are observed, e.g., in Lusoga [JE16] *embidhi*, Gwere [JE17] *mbizi*, Masaaba [JE31] *imbizi* etc. In the eastern shore of the lake, *<beche>* is the common form, e.g., Saamia [JE34] *embeche*, Suba [JE403] *embichi*, and Kuria [JE43] *embeshe*. Finally in the western part of the lake, *<punu>* and the related forms are shared among Nyoro-Ganda group [JE10] in Uganda as well as in Haya-Jita group [JE20] in Tanzania. Like in the case of ‘rat’ (cf. Shinagawa and Komori 2022a), we can also find out a lexical unity among the languages spoken in the corridor between Lake Tanganyika and Lake Rukwa [M10–20], where *<kapoli>* and the related forms are commonly used.

Fig. 1 Geographical distribution of the word ‘pig’

Forms traced back to reconstructed PB forms	Other common forms
○ *-gòdòbè; *-gòdòbì	∨ <punu>
⊙ *-gòdòbè; *-gòdòbì <gubi>	∧ <kapoli>
▽ *-gòdò	= <beche>
	<mbizi>
	Ψ <goy>

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